

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: AKYEREFI-MENSAH****FIRST NAME: ISAAC WILLIAM****PROGRAM CODE: DIRD****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. An academic essay aims to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence. How will you explain to your students what a good essay is?

A good essay must have a well-defined thesis statement and an argument, present a developed thesis by reasoning and evidence, and cite the supporting evidence and information from credible sources or academic texts.¹

A good essay should have an answer to the question under discussion with supporting evidence.

A good essay should have a good plan and present information without recourse to citing sources.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*. 3rd ed. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 1.

- A good essay must have a statement of the problem and answers to the problem with supporting evidence from whatever source.
2. What is the basic structure and framework a good essay should follow to help answer the question you wish to address logically and coherently?
- The structure and framework of a good essay is to communicate your ideas and answers to the question with supporting evidence must have an introduction, a body, and a conclusion.²**
- The structure and framework of a good essay is to answer questions to the statement of the problem must have an introduction and conclusion.
- The structure and framework of a good essay is to communicate your ideas and answers to the question with supporting evidence must have a body and a conclusion.
- The structure and framework of a good essay is to communicate your ideas and answers to the question with supporting evidence that must have an introduction, a body, paragraphs, and a conclusion.
3. When writing essays and academic papers, one of the critical things the writer should do is to avoid plagiarism. What is plagiarism, and why should writers avoid it?
- Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information. Not citing and giving credit**

² Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*. 3rd ed., 3.

to the authors of your sources is wrong and unethical; it is unfair and a serious academic offense that can have serious consequences.³

- Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information. It is not a big deal to cite and not give credit to the authors of your sources.
- Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information. It is wrong, though; if we do not cite and give credit to the authors of our sources, it may not have any serious consequences.
- Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information. Every writer builds on other people's work; therefore, plagiarism should not be an issue.

4. What is research, and what are its intended purposes?

- Research is a "process of systematic inquiry to answer a question that only the researcher and others want to solve." Through quality research, a solution to outstanding problems is unraveled to the benefit of all if the finding is accurately presented.⁴**

³ Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*. 3rd ed., 3.

⁴ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 9th ed. Revised by Wayne C. Booth, et al. (Chicago and London: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 19.

- Research is a process of inquiry to answer a question that only the researcher wants to solve. Through research, solutions to outstanding problems are unraveled to benefit all if the finding is accurately presented.
 - Research is a process of systematic inquiry to answer a question that only the researcher wants to solve. Through research, the researcher becomes famous.
 - Research is a process of systematic inquiry to answer a question that others want to solve. Through research, solutions to outstanding problems are unraveled to benefit all if the finding is accurately presented.
5. Explain how to define a research project to your students.
- We define a research project by stating the parameters we shall operate within. To define a research project, we must clearly state the topic we want to investigate, question the topic to reveal the problems at stake and the answers we must provide, and must provisionally explain the prime importance to serve as the basis for the project with supporting evidence.⁵**
 - We define a research project by stating the parameters we shall operate within. To define a research project, we may state the topic we want to investigate and the prime importance of serving as the basis for the project with supporting evidence.
 - We define a research project by stating the parameters we shall operate within. To define a research project, we must question the topic to reveal the problems at stake and the answers we must provide.

⁵ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 23.

- We define a research project by stating the parameters we shall operate within. To define a research project, we must not necessarily state the topic we want to investigate or question the topic to reveal the problems at stake and the answers we must provide. However, we must provisionally explain the prime importance of serving as the basis for the project with supporting evidence.
6. What is a research formula? How can you help a beginner to understand a research problem?
- A research formula expresses how experienced researchers think in pursuing their research projects. The procedure to understanding a research problem is: "Topic: I am working on X. Question: because I want to find Y. Significance: so that I can help others to understand Z."⁶**
- A research formula expresses how experienced researchers think in pursuing their research projects. The procedure to understanding a research problem is Topic: I am working on X. Significance: to help others understand Y.
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⁶ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 32.

7. What is the importance of source citation?

Source citation is a feature of every quality research work that indicates a reference to a book for ideas or information through a quotation, paraphrasing, and summary as supporting evidence as to where we got our information. Source citation gives credit and recognition to the sources we have borrowed our information. It gives credibility to our work and guards the researcher against plagiarism.⁷

Source citation is a quotation, paraphrasing, and summary of research work. Source citation gives credit and recognition to the sources we have borrowed our information. It gives credibility to our work and guards the researcher against plagiarism.

Source citation supports evidence of where we got our information for the research work. Source citation gives credit and recognition to the sources we have borrowed our information. It gives credibility to our work and guards the researcher against plagiarism.

Source citation is an antidote to plagiarism. It gives credit and recognition to the sources we have borrowed our information. It gives credibility to our work and guards the researcher against plagiarism.

8. How will you explain the requirements for citation to a beginner in research work?

Requirements for citation give details and relevant information about what occasion we should cite our sources and what we must include in the

⁷ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 143-144.

publication information. They may consist of those who created the work: the author, editor, or translator; data identifying the text represented by titles and subtitles of the work, volume number, edition number or other information, page numbers or other locating information; the publishers, journal or others responsible for making the work available; date of publication which may be the year of publication and sometimes the season, months, specific days and the links to information accessed online or in a database to help readers to find them.⁸

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⁸ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 144-145.

information; the publishers, journal, or others responsible for making the work available; and the links to information accessed online or in a database to help readers to find them.

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9. Briefly explain the two basic citation styles and give examples of each.

- The two most common citation styles used are notes-bibliography and author-date Style, called the Turabian or Chicago source citation system. In a notes-bibliography style, we acknowledge our source by placing a superscript number at the end of the sentence that carries ideas or information, or quotation from the sources we consulted by indicating the author, the title, and publication information with appropriate page numbers corresponding to the superscript number. Footnotes are placed at the end of the page, whereas the endnotes are placed at the end of a chapter. Example, Notes – Angela Duckworth, *Grit: The Power of Passion and Perseverance* (New York: Scribner, 2016), 90. Bibliography – Duckworth, Angela. *Grit: The Power of***

Passion and Perseverance. New York: Scribner, 2016. In author-date Style is signaled by placing a parenthetical with the author's last name, date of publication, and page number, for example (Turabian 2018, 23).⁹

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⁹ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 145-146.

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10. Outline the basic features or components of a completed dissertation or thesis.

The composition of A complete dissertation or thesis may include front matters, including the title page, copyright, abstract, dedication, acknowledgment, and table of content. The second feature is the dissertation chapters comprising an introduction, literature review, methodology and research approach, findings- analysis, interpretation, and synthesis of findings, conclusions, and recommendations, including the epilogue, afterword, or final thoughts. The last feature is the back matters which include appendices, and references.¹⁰

The composition of A complete dissertation or thesis may include front matters, including the title page, copyright, abstract, dedication, acknowledgment, and table of content. The second feature is the dissertation chapters comprising an

¹⁰ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie F. Volpe, *Completing Your Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to the End* 4th ed. (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019), 4-37.

- introduction, literature review, methodology and research approach, findings-analysis, interpretation, and synthesis of findings, conclusions, and recommendations, including the epilogue, afterword, or final thoughts.
- A complete dissertation or thesis may include chapters comprising an introduction, literature review, methodology, research approach, findings- analysis, interpretation, synthesis of findings, conclusions, and recommendations, including the epilogue, afterword, or final thoughts. The last feature is the back matters which include appendices and references.
 - The composition of A complete dissertation or thesis may include front matters, including the title page, copyright, abstract, dedication, acknowledgment, and table of content. The last feature is the back matters which include appendices and references.

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